

rice farmers were included in the field investigation. A pretested questionnaire was used to gather data just after the 2001-02 maha season (Apr-May). A scoring procedure was applied to rank farmers' views on technology dissemination. Rank 1 is given seven points and rank 7 is given one point. Table 1 shows the various technologies as ranked by farmers in terms of importance. Sixty-three farmers had identified varietal recommendations as the most important technology disseminated. Sixteen farmers gave the same technology a ranking of 2. The total score for each technology is the sum of the products of the number of farmer-respondents in a rank class multiplied by the corresponding score point.

The technological innovations that have been disseminated were ranked by farmers thus: varieties (1), fertilizer (2), pest and disease control methods (3), irrigation methods (4), weed control methods (5), land preparation methods (6), and transplanting methods (7).

Similarly, farmer needs were also identified using the same ranking procedure. Table 2 shows the ranking of these needs.

The most important need identified by rice farmers is to gain knowledge on organic farming (Table 2). Market information, training, input supply, credit facilities, and business counseling, in that order, were also deemed important.

The study reveals that the technologies disseminated do not match the farmers' needs. It is crucial that extension efforts be reoriented to serve the current needs pointed out by farmers.

Table 1. Farmers' ranking of various technologies in terms of importance.

Technology	Rank ^a							Total ^b score	Final rank
	1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
Varietal recommendations	63	16	9	3	3	4	2	613	1
Fertilizer recommendations	8	44	16	11	13	4	4	495	2
Pest and disease control methods	7	9	26	32	13	7	6	420	3
Weed control methods	1	9	19	20	22	20	9	351	5
Land preparation methods	3	5	14	20	19	23	16	320	6
Irrigation methods	12	15	9	8	14	28	14	363	4
Transplanting methods	7	2	7	7	16	14	47	247	7

^aRank 1 is given seven points; rank 7 is given one point. ^bSum of products of number of farmer-respondents multiplied by corresponding score point.

Table 2. Farmers' ranking of actual needs.

Need	Rank ^a						Total ^b score	Final rank
	1	2	3	4	5	6		
Loan/credit	7	8	5	14	42	24	252	5
Knowledge on organic farming	47	24	13	12	3	1	497	1
Market information	12	26	37	17	7	1	416	2
Training	9	28	32	21	8	2	403	3
Input supply	24	8	9	28	24	7	359	4
Business counseling	0	3	4	9	16	68	158	6

^aRank 1 is given six points; rank 6 is given one point. ^bSum of products of number of farmer-respondents multiplied by corresponding score point.

Advance estimation of rice production in India using weather indices

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Estimation of crop production from area and yield estimates based on sample surveys and crop-cutting experiments, an approach currently being followed in India, can give final estimates only after the crops are actually harvested. However, various

policy decisions related to pricing, marketing, export/import, distribution, etc., necessitate the use of advance estimates. A simple model based on weather indices can be used to obtain accurate estimates of annual rice production even before the crop

is harvested.

Crop production in India largely depends on the summer monsoon (June to September), which provides about 80–90% of annual rainfall in most parts of the country. The summer monsoon rainfall is the main source of

water for the kharif crop. Rainwater stored as soil moisture and other water resources (lakes, reservoirs, and rivers) are also important for the *rabi*—and other irrigated crops. Parthasarathy et al (1988) have estimated the annual food-grain production in the country using the all-India summer monsoon rainfall data. The rainfall data, however, showed significant variations in time and space. To obtain more accurate production estimates, the temporal and spatial variations of monsoon rainfall were also included in the model through suitable weather indices.

Rice, the most important crop in India, is currently grown on 44.6 million ha, contributing about 42% of total food-grain production. The time series of annual rice production constitutes a prominently increasing trend, which is superimposed onto year-to-year fluctuations (Fig. 1a). The increasing trend—which is attributed to nonmeteorological factors such as increased gross sown area, improved technology, fertilizer application, pest and disease control, etc.—has been estimated by fitting an exponential equation (Mooley et al 1981, Parthasarathy et al 1988) of the following form into the historical annual rice production data for the period 1950-2000:

$$\text{Trend} = \text{EXP} (0.0272931 * \text{YEAR}) * 1.79309\text{E-}22 \dots \dots \dots (1)$$

(R² = 0.96)

As previously stated, the year-to-year fluctuations in rice production are mainly due to variations in monsoon rainfall and can be estimated from weather indices. To identify suitable weather indices, production indices (PI) of rice have been obtained (Fig. 1b) by eliminating the

trend component (obtained from Eq. 1) from actual production in each year:

$$\text{PI} = (\text{Production}/\text{trend}) * 100 \dots (2)$$

To include intraseasonal and spatial variations of monsoon rainfall in the estimation model, monthly (June-September) rainfall indices (RI) have been constructed from the area-weighted rainfall of the subdivisions (See table), with which the annual rice PI has significant correlations—i.e., $\sum \text{Ri} * \text{Ai}$, where Ri is rainfall and Ai is area of the ith subdivision. Similarly, in considering year-to-year variations of monsoon rainfall, the southern oscillation index (SOI) has been included in the model. SOI—the index that measures the atmospheric pressure difference be-

tween Tahiti and Darwin—is known to have a significant relationship with interannual variability of the Indian summer monsoon. A multiple regression model has been developed to estimate the annual rice PI from the monthly RIs and SOI as follows:

$$\text{PI} = 58.293 + 0.0396 * \text{RI} + 0.088 * \text{SOI} + 0.0381 * \text{RI} + 0.0253 * \text{SOI} \dots (3)$$

(R² = 0.70)

This model explains nearly 70% of the variance in PI. Annual rice production is evaluated from the PI estimated above and the trend value (T) is estimated from equation 1: production = (PI*T)/100. The estimates of annual rice production, which can be obtained by October (well before the crops are harvested), are found to be in close agreement (within

Subdivisions considered for construction of monthly rainfall indices.

Month	Meteorological subdivisions ^a
June	Jharkhand, east Madhya Pradesh, Konkan and Goa, Madhya Maharashtra, Marathwada, Vidarbha, coastal Andhra Pradesh, and Telangana
July	East Uttar Pradesh, west Uttar Pradesh, Haryana, Punjab, east Madhya Pradesh, Rayalaseema, Tamil Nadu, north interior Karnataka, and south interior Karnataka
August	Jharkhand, Haryana, east Rajasthan, east Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat, Marathwada, Vidarbha, and Telangana
September	Sub-Himalayan West Bengal, Gangetic West Bengal, Orissa, west Uttar Pradesh, Haryana, east Rajasthan, west Madhya Pradesh, east Madhya Pradesh, Gujarat, Saurashtra & Kutch, coastal Andhra Pradesh, and coastal Karnataka

^aFor reference map, see Parthasarathy et al (1988).

Fig. 1. All-India annual rice production (a) and production index (b), 1950-2000.

±5%, except in a few years) with actual values (Fig. 2). The all-India annual rice production for 2001-02 was predicted to be 93.1 million t (with a deviation of +2% from actual values) in October 2001, vis-à-vis the official final estimate of 91.6 million t available in June 2002, 8 mo in advance.

References

- Mooley DA, Parthasarathy B, Sontakke NA, Munot AA. 1981. Annual rainwater over India, its variability and impact on the economy. *J. Climatol.* 1:167-186.
- Parthasarathy B, Munot AA, Kothawale DR. 1988. Regression model for estimation of Indian foodgrain production from summer monsoon rainfall. *Agric. For. Meteorol.* 42:167-182.

Fig. 2. Actual and estimated values of annual rice production in India during model development (1950-89) and verification (1990-2000) periods.

Impact of soil reclamation on productivity, income, and employment of rice farmers: a case study of the Krishnagiri Reservoir Project area

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The area of salt-affected soils is increasing with time. In India, nearly 7 million ha are affected by the salt problem and, in Tamil Nadu state alone, this problem is acute on an area of 0.3 million ha (Parshad 1989). The salt problem alone accounts for a 20–80% reduction in yield. Efforts to reclaim and re-vegetate these soils require appropriate technologies. Improper diagnoses and the adoption of inappropriate technologies would result in a waste of time and scarce resources.

A case study was undertaken in the Krishnagiri Reservoir Project (KRP) area to find out the impact of soil reclamation on rice

productivity, income, and employment of rice farmers. The data were collected in the KRP area in Dharmapuri District of Tamil Nadu, India. Agriculture is the major means of livelihood of the people. A variety of agricultural crops such as cereals, millet, and pulses and horticultural crops such as mango and tomato are grown in the dry farming areas of this tract. Among the food crops, rice occupies a pivotal place in the food and livelihood systems of the human and livestock population of this district. In Dharmapuri District, rice is grown on about 64,000 ha. Traditionally grown in two seasons,

wet (July–November) and dry (December–March), by canal and well irrigation, respectively, rice has a productivity of 3.2 t ha⁻¹ (Kannaiyan 2002). Nearly 12% of the total rice area has salinity-related problems. The KRP area, where rice alone could be cultivated, faces serious salt problems.

We obtained data on the cost of rice cultivation, cost of reclamation, and impact of reclamation on productivity, income, and employment of farmers in the KRP command area.

The farmers were grouped into three on the basis of the location of their farmholding along the canal area of the reservoir—